

THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF KARAKUL BREEDING IN THE BUKHARA EMIRATE

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ABSTRACT

The production of karakul pelts during the period of the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate was one of the important sectors in the economy of Central Asia. This study examines the breeding of karakul sheep in the territories of the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate, the production of high-quality pelts, and the significance of these products in domestic and foreign markets. Particular attention is given to the export of karakul pelts through trade routes to Russia, Europe, and other regions, which contributed to the development of economic relations. In addition, the study analyzes information about the local population engaged in karakul breeding, traditional livestock practices, and production methods..

Introduction

Karakul breeding occupied an important place in the economic life of the Bukhara Emirate and was considered one of the most developed branches of animal husbandry. Favorable natural and climatic conditions, extensive desert and semi-desert pastures, as well as the long-standing experience of local livestock breeders created broad opportunities for the development of Karakul sheep breeding. The pelts obtained from Karakul sheep were highly valued not only in local markets but also in international trade due to their quality, durability, and unique appearance.

The formation and development of Karakul breeding in the Bukhara Emirate took place over several historical stages. In the early period, the industry mainly developed on the basis of traditional breeding methods and nomadic pastoral practices. Later, with the expansion of trade relations and the growing demand for Karakul pelts in foreign markets, especially in Russia and Europe, this sector gradually gained economic importance. By the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, Karakul breeding had become one of the leading export-oriented sectors of the emirate's economy.

The development of Karakul breeding also contributed to the expansion of trade relations between the Bukhara Emirate and neighboring countries. Merchants and trade companies were actively involved in the purchase and export of Karakul pelts, which increased the role of the emirate in international markets. At the same time, scientific interest in Karakul sheep breeding began to grow, and research related to breeding, productivity, and adaptation attracted the attention of foreign specialists.

This study aims to examine the formation and stages of development of Karakul breeding in the Bukhara Emirate, as well as its economic significance and role in international trade relations.

Literature review

A number of historical sources and scientific publications are of great importance in studying the history of Karakul pelt production in the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate. In researching this topic, first of all, general historical works devoted to the development of livestock farming in Central Asia are widely used. In particular, the studies of scholars such as Boris Vladimirovich Lunin, Alexander Yulyevich Yakubovsky, and Sergey Pavlovich Tolstov serve as important scientific sources in explaining the formation and development of livestock farming and trade relations in the region.

In addition, modern studies related to the history of Uzbekistan also provide important information about the economic significance of Karakul breeding. In particular, the works of researchers such as Asqar Asqarov, Ravshan Shamsutdinov, and Qahramon Rajabov extensively analyze the economic life, livestock sectors, and trade relations of the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate.

Discussion and results

Uzbekistan is one of the world's leading countries in the production of Karakul pelts and possesses many years of experience in this field. Karakul sheep were mainly raised in the Karakum Desert and Kyzylkum Desert deserts, where the animals were supplied with water from deep wells. In addition, Karakul sheep were also bred in the undeveloped lands along the rivers Amu Darya, Syr Darya, Zarafshan River, Qashqadaryo Region, and Murghab River. During the period of the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate, the best flocks of Karakul sheep were bred in the regions of Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Karki, and Karakalpakstan. Most of these sheep belonged to small landowners who were completely dependent on wealthy estate owners. During this period, winter fodder was not prepared for Karakul sheep, and they grazed on pastures throughout the year. Therefore, during severe winters, a significant part of the sheep population, and in some years up to 90 percent, perished [1].

Karakul pelts from Uzbekistan were also exported to various countries around the world. For example, between 1840 and 1850, 427,797 Karakul pelts were transported from Bukhara to Russia through the Orenburg route, while 60,583 pelts were exported through Troitsk.

The export of Karakul pelts from Bukhara to Iran increased after 1844. Due to the prohibition of direct trade relations between the Bukhara Emirate and the British, the government of United Kingdom was forced to purchase Karakul pelts indirectly through Iranian merchants. Through England, Karakul pelts spread across Europe and were sold in European markets at prices comparable to gold [2].

Among the exported varieties of Karakul pelts, the bluish-gray type produced in the Qarshi Bekdom occupied a special place. The varieties known as "doador" and "karpak" (the pelts of prematurely born lambs) were especially famous and were widely sold to Russia, United Kingdom, Turkey, China, India, and Iran. Trade exchange among these states steadily increased. For example, Bukhara's exports to Russia rose from 830,600 rubles in 1865 to 3,125,000 rubles in 1911–1913. About 88 percent of the exports and 90 percent of the

imports of the Bukhara Emirate were connected with Russia. Livestock farms also oriented their production toward export markets. As a result, while Bukhara exported only 30–40 thousand Karakul pelts in the mid-nineteenth century, this number reached 1.5 million pelts in 1911–1914 [3]. However, due to war and economic crises, Bukhara's exports sharply declined, falling from 40–45 million rubles to only 1 million rubles by 1921.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, Karakul breeding was one of the main sources of income for the Bukhara Emirate. Karakul pelts were highly valued in the markets of Russia and Europe and were sold at auctions in Saint Petersburg, as well as at fairs in Lyon, Nizhny Novgorod, and Makar. "In 1908 alone, 1.7 million Karakul pelts were sold at the Nizhny Novgorod Fair. Half of the sold Karakul pelts were purchased by Russian companies and the local population, while the remaining half was bought by foreign firms" [4].

The Nizhny Novgorod Fair was not only a major market for Karakul pelts but also for products made from them. It featured markets for the latest styles of clothing, and there was particularly strong demand for long coats made of Karakul fur for women [5]. In 1907, British merchants purchased Bukhara Karakul pelts in bulk at prices ranging from 98 to 104 rubles per piece on site, while high-quality pelts were bought for 115–120 rubles each. Small Karakul fur pieces, depending on their quality, were purchased for 52–63 rubles and up to 65–75 rubles. Russian merchants valued Karakul pelts lower than the British and paid around 92 rubles per piece [6].

Merchants of the Emir of Bukhara traded Karakul pelts in a number of major cities in Europe and Asia. Karakul pelts produced in regions such as Kattakurgan and Khujand were valued lower than those processed in Bukhara and were sold for around 85–88 rubles. In later years, due to the increasing demand for Karakul pelts from foreign countries, their prices also continued to rise. For example, in 1909 the price of Karakul pelts at Russian fairs increased to 110–130 rubles.

Most of the Karakul-producing countries imported Karakul sheep mainly from Uzbekistan for breeding purposes. For instance, in 1881, on the initiative of the Poltava Agricultural Society, Bukhara Karakul sheep were first brought to the territory of Ukraine for breeding. This society requested permission from the Department of Agriculture to establish a special breeding station for purebred Karakul sheep and to expand their population. Zootechnical scientists such as M.S. Karpov, M.F. Ivanov, R.R. Pravokhenskiy, and I. Ilchevskiy conducted the first experiments on Karakul sheep [7]. Several other ryбepниas of the empire also joined this initiative, and according to the "Kharkov Province Bulletin," the funds allocated for this purpose amounted to 4,500 rubles in 1888 [8]. The Poltava Agricultural Society allocated 60 rubles for the purchase of one purebred Karakul sheep and 75–85 rubles for a lamb. Specialists of the society made considerable efforts to breed Karakul sheep under new environmental conditions. In 1888, a Karakul breeding farm was established in Ukraine [9].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the production of Karakul pelts in the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate was one of the important branches of livestock farming and occupied a significant place in the economic life of the region. Favorable climatic conditions, the existence of vast pastures, and the rich experience of the local population in animal husbandry created

opportunities for breeding Karakul sheep and producing high-quality pelts. Karakul pelts played an important role not only in meeting domestic needs but also in developing foreign trade relations. Through this sector, the states of Bukhara and Khiva expanded their trade and economic relations and contributed to the stable development of the regional economy.

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